

NEW UZBEKISTAN - NEW SPIRITUAL SPACE**Sharipov Abdukhakimjon Ziyoiddinovich***Associate professor of Pedagogical Institute of Bukhara State University**Bukhara, Uzbekistan**abduhakim-83@mail.ru*

Abstract: This article examines the role of economic, legal and political reforms in the development strategy of New Uzbekistan, as well as the role of moral renewal in solving world problems. The article also philosophically analyzes the issue of approaching the issues of ensuring peace based on the requirements of high cultural and universal human values.

Keywords: development, spiritual renewal, national values, perfect man, spiritual reforms, new history, spiritual space

Today, the 21st century has started a new era in the history of human. In other words, a new stage and process of renewal has begun in the development of man and society. Changes in society are a clear expression of large-scale changes in the world's economic, spiritual, and social-political processes. The process of general human renewal began to have a positive effect on the fate of one country first, then on a number of states, countries, society, and people's lives. Each country began to participate in the process of innovative development at the level of its economic potential, scientific-educational and spiritual level, perfection. Therefore, in the process of global changes, New Uzbekistan is taking a unique and suitable position as a country with its unique socio-political and spiritual renewal program.

The deep reforms and reformational political renewals that are being carried out in Uzbekistan today are in common with the modern world civilization. Targeted improvement of socio-economic and spiritual life, development of this environment in the spirit of harmony of universal and national values, comprehensive expansion of the environment of liberalism is not only through calling, but also through the strategy of actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic

of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 to start the process of renewal in the country practical steps were taken.

As a result of strategic reforms, improvement of state and society construction, ensuring the rule of law and further reforming the judicial system, further developing and liberalizing the economy, developing the social sphere, ensuring security, inter-ethnic harmony and religious tolerance, drastical reform of the spheres of conducting foreign policy in a deeply thought-out, mutually beneficial and practical spirit will make it possible to create a renewed state, a changed society and a perfect person.

Today, it is confirmed that the purposeful management of the state and society, the processes of personal renewal, required mental courage, pragmatic policy, and political will and perseverance. After all, this management is being implemented in the conditions of laborious and complicated socio-political events, ideological influence and pressure.

New Uzbekistan has begun to implement the process of large-scale renewal in two interconnected directions:

First, it organizes reforms in the internal world of the country, i.e. economy, spirituality, politics and lifestyle, carried out on the basis of the principles of popular consent;

Secondly, forming the image of Uzbekistan in the international community, that is, establishing friendly neighborly relations, mutual cooperation relations, pragmatic foreign policy, transition to a culture of peace, deepening of inter-ethnic and inter-religious tolerance relations, terrorism, which poses a common threat to humanity, drug business, establishing a foundation for deep cooperation with the structures of international organizations against extremism, and other activities.

In the country, the strategies of spiritual growth, restoration of national values, education of a generation loyal to the traditions of succession and introduction into practice began to be implemented. In particular, the fact that Uzbekistan's strategy of fundamentally renewing society, reforming all areas, and changing them based on new ideas is fully approved and supported by the world community indicates that

the Uzbek character has changed, and the people's mind, spirit, and mentality are being renewed. The final results of the renewal processes are to open a wide way for the full emergence of human potential, the manifestation of personal potential, potential reserves.

In general, this chosen path is the way to form a civil society in which human interests are fully protected, and his will and freedom are fully legally guaranteed. This, of course, requires the development of a comprehensive and complete system of creating a transparent society by changing the human mind and thinking, renewing the way of life.

In the process of reforms being implemented in Uzbekistan, spiritual reforms take a special place. This way is important in deepening the processes of democracy, in increasing the activity of citizens in liberating the society. At the moment, as the foundation of the “Third Renaissance” of fundamental changes, it is a unique contribution to the experience of world development strategies. In other words, such a model of society development is being formed in New Uzbekistan and is being evaluated as an effective direction of social management in accordance with international standards.

Spirituality is a social phenomenon that always accompanies material life, is an integral part of the life of a person, people and society, and is a criterion of human views. Every enlightened person can give a different definition to this term, which has a very deep and comprehensive meaning, based on his life views, self-thought and worldview. This concept, which makes a person a person and is closely connected with his mind and spirit, has a special importance in the life of every person, society, nation and people, which cannot be measured by anything.

Moreover, spirituality has a proportional effect on both the general picture of society and the intellectual-spiritual image of each individual. The spiritual and educational level of citizens, in turn, changes the general state of society. Renewed moral maturity and social consciousness determine the progress of society and create new possibilities for development.

It is worth noting that each new generation requires a new history, creates it, improves it. But this is clear that spirituality will retain its importance as a broad concept that expresses the laws and principles of its field. In this regard, in the creation of a new spiritual space in Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the system of spirituality as a set of requirements and rules that regulate social relations and interactions between people, as well as the system of spiritual values, customs and traditions, ideals, noble ideas and goals. So, spirituality expresses a whole set of phenomena consisting of ethics, culture, enlightenment, religion and educational system, creative activity of a person improving himself and the world in which he lives, perfection, his spiritual image and a set of educational qualities.

In the process of building a new spiritual space:

First of all, the events taking place in people's lives and society as a whole require certain changes in the consciousness and spirituality of the individual.

Secondly, spirituality has a great influence on the origin and occurrence of changes in reality. If spirituality is not renewed and enriched, it would become obsolete very soon and become a phenomenon that causes crisis rather than a factor of development. Today, the new Uzbekistan is a turning point in the development of society, and serious changes are taking place in spirituality during the period of fundamental reforms.

At this point, it is appropriate to compare the material and spiritual world, which is necessary for realizing human dreams and living a conscious life, to the two wings of a flying bird. So, if these two important factors become a true harmony, only then the processes of improvement and renewal will take place in the life of a person, state and society.

In conclusion, every person and society who aspires to achieve high development can achieve positive results only if they develop their lives on the basis of the dialectical and integral connection of material and spiritual harmony. All this is a vivid expression of how the path of economic development fed by Uzbek spiritual values, customs and traditions has a positive effect on the life of the society. The most important thing is that the material and spiritual processes are developed

in a mutually proportional way in Uzbekistan, which serves as a solid guarantee of political and social stability and development.

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